

ARTERIAL STIFFNESS INDEX BETA AND CARDIO-ANKLE VASCULAR INDEX INHERENTLY DEPEND ON BLOOD PRESSURE, BUT CAN BE READILY CORRECTED

SUPPLEMENTAL DIGITAL CONTENT 1

DETAILED METHODS

Derivation of Eq. 4 of the main article

Eq. 1 of the main article can be re-arranged to

$$d = d_{\text{ref}} \left(1 + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right)}{\beta_0} \right). \quad (\text{S1})$$

Using this equation, we find an expression for systolic (d_s) and diastolic diameter (d_d):

$$d_s = d_{\text{ref}} \left(1 + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right)}{\beta_0} \right) \text{ and } d_d = d_{\text{ref}} \left(1 + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right)}{\beta_0} \right); \quad (\text{S2})$$

and fill these in into Eq. 3 of the main article:

$$\beta = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{d_{\text{ref}} \left(1 + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right)}{\beta_0} \right) - d_{\text{ref}} \left(1 + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}}\right)}{\beta_0} \right)}. \quad (\text{S3})$$

Simplification of the denominator leads to

$$\beta = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{ref}}\right)}{1 + \frac{\beta_0}{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right)} - 1}} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\frac{\beta_0 + \ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{ref}}\right)}{\beta_0} - 1}} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0}{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0}}, \quad (S4)$$

and further to

$$\beta = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0}{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0} - \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0}{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0}} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{ref}}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0}} = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0\right) \ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_{ref}}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right)}. \quad (S5)$$

Using the identity $\ln(a/b) = \ln(a) - \ln(b)$ to further simplify the denominator, we obtain

$$\beta = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0\right) \ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\ln(P_s) - \ln(P_{ref}) - \ln(P_d) + \ln(P_{ref})} = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0\right) \ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\ln(P_s) - \ln(P_d)} = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0\right) \ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{P_s}{P_d}\right)}, \quad (S6)$$

and finally

$$\beta = \ln\left(\frac{P_d}{P_{ref}}\right) + \beta_0. \quad (S7)$$

Bramwell-Hill relationship

Bramwell and Hill derived the relationship between local pressure (P) and cross-sectional area (A) and PWV [1]:

$$PWV = \sqrt{\frac{dP}{dA} \frac{A}{\rho}}, \quad (S8)$$

in which $\rho = 1050 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ is the blood mass density.

This equation can be re-written in terms of diameter (d):

$$PWV = \sqrt{\frac{dP}{dd} \frac{d}{2\rho}}. \quad (S9)$$

For use in the conventional CAVI formula, this equation is approximated by [2]:

$$PWV \approx \sqrt{\frac{P_s - P_d}{2(d_s - d_d)} \frac{d_d}{\rho}}. \quad (S10)$$

Derivation of the true pulse wave velocity at points on an exponential pressure-diameter curve (Eq. 1 of the main article) and obtaining a pressure-independent formula for CAVI

The Bramwell-Hill equation contains a derivative of pressure to area ($\frac{dP}{dA}$, Eq. S8) or to diameter ($\frac{dP}{dd}$, Eq. S9). This derivative can be readily obtained by differentiating Eq. 1 (main article) with respect to d :

$$\frac{dP}{dd} = \frac{\beta_0}{d_{\text{ref}}} P_{\text{ref}} e^{\beta_0 \left(\frac{d}{d_{\text{ref}}} - 1 \right)} = \frac{\beta_0}{d_{\text{ref}}} P. \quad (\text{S11})$$

Combining this equation with Eq. S9 for $P = P_d$ yields [3]

$$\text{PWV} = \sqrt{P_d \frac{d_d}{d_{\text{ref}}} \frac{\beta_0}{2\rho}}. \quad (\text{S12})$$

Filling in d_d from Eq. S2 yields

$$\text{PWV} = \sqrt{\frac{P_d}{2\rho} \left(\ln \left(\frac{P_d}{P_{\text{ref}}} \right) + \beta_0 \right)}. \quad (\text{S13})$$

Squaring this equation and rearranging yields Eq. 9 of the main article.

Generation of example dataset

In order to gain insight into the magnitude of the blood pressure dependence of CAVI, we computer-generated measurement data. In the simulated subjects, an anti-hypertensive treatment-induced blood pressure lowering was simulated, while assuming that the artery wall structure and function remained unaltered. I.e., subjects remained on their exponential P - d relationship (Eq. 1, main article), and β_0 did not change. Measurement data were generated by (i) drawing numbers from normal distributions (assuming biological spread but no measurement noise) and (ii) subsequently adding measurement noise.

Method for generation of measurement data

In this section $N(\mu, \sigma)$ denotes independent samples drawn from a normal distribution with mean μ and standard deviation σ . Subscripts bl and fu indicate baseline and

follow-up, respectively. Subscript nf indicates "noise-free" values, i.e., these do not contain measurement noise. The following data were generated:

- An intrinsic stiffness index (β_0) for each subject was drawn from $N(10,2)$.
- Baseline diastolic blood pressures ($P_{d,bl,nf}$) were drawn from $N(110 \text{ mmHg}, 10 \text{ mmHg})$. Baseline pulse pressures ($P_{p,bl,nf}$) were drawn from $N(50 \text{ mmHg}, 10 \text{ mmHg})$. Systolic pressure ($P_{s,bl,nf}$) was calculated as the sum of diastolic and pulse pressures. Baseline PWV ($PWV_{bl,nf}$) was subsequently calculated from $P_{d,bl,nf}$ and β_0 by means of Eq. S13. Note that PWV is calculated (or "measured") using the equation that is based on the true, non-approximated $\frac{dP}{dd}$.
- Follow-up diastolic blood pressures ($P_{d,fu,nf}$) were drawn from $N(80 \text{ mmHg}, 10 \text{ mmHg})$. Follow-up pulse pressures ($P_{p,fu,nf}$) were drawn from $N(40 \text{ mmHg}, 10 \text{ mmHg})$. Systolic pressure ($P_{s,fu,nf}$) was calculated as the sum of diastolic and pulse pressures. Follow-up PWV ($PWV_{fu,nf}$) was again calculated using Eq. S13.

Normally-distributed, additive, random measurement noise was added to DBP, SBP and PWV at both baseline and follow-up. Noise on DBP and SBP measurements was assumed to be zero-mean and independent. Using data from a previous study [4], we calculated intra-subject SD of DBP as the square root of the mean of all individual variances [5], resulting in an intra-subject SD of 5.0 mmHg.

If measurement noise is assumed to be the sole source of the repeatability variation, one can generate BP noise by drawing independent samples from $N(0, 5.0 \text{ mmHg})$.

Repeatability of PWV measurements was assessed by Salvi et al. [6]. For their reference method, the SphygmoCor (AtCor, Sydney, Australia) device, they report a repeatability of 1.44 m/s. Salvi et al. defined repeatability as *two* times the standard deviation of the *difference* between two measurements. This led to a standard deviation in one measurement of $\frac{1.44}{2\sqrt{2}}$ m/s. Therefore, we generated PWV measurement noise by drawing samples from $N\left(0, \frac{1.44}{2\sqrt{2}} \text{ m/s}\right)$.

Measured CAVI and $CAVI_0$ were calculated using Eq. 7 and 9 (main article), respectively, filling in SBP, DBP and PWV including measurement noise.

Simulation protocol

First, we generated measurement data as described above for a large number of subjects ($n = 10^6$). This yields robust estimates of the mean and standard deviation of CAVI in this simulated population, before and after simulated blood pressure lowering. Using these values, we performed a sample size calculation, determining the number of subjects that, at a probability (power) of 0.8, would lead to a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$) in CAVI between baseline and follow-up.

Second, we generated measurement data in the number of subjects that resulted from the sample size calculation. Results from this simulation are reported.

SUPPLEMENTAL REFERENCES

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